

CaRCC 2024 Annual Retreat Report

The Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) held its annual strategy and planning retreat October 13-15, 2024, at The Westin hotel in Arlington, Virginia. The retreat was organized in a hybrid format, with both in-person and virtual attendance via Zoom. The retreat included 37 participants, with 34 attending in person in Washington, D.C. and 3 participating remotely via Zoom. Attendees represented a diverse range of institutions including research universities, liberal arts colleges, regional networks, and national organizations. The three-day event included two days focused on CaRCC strategy and planning, followed by a joint session with the Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC).

Goals of the 2024 Annual Retreat included:

- Evaluating the state of CaRCC's organizational structure and activities
- Planning for financial sustainability
- Enhancing volunteer recruitment and management
- Improving outreach to non-R1 institutions
- Strengthening governance and planning processes

Day 1 focused on organizational assessment and opportunities, with presentations from:

- People Network tracks
- Interest Groups
- Working Groups
- Operations Groups
- Financial Models Committee

Day 2 featured unconference sessions addressing key strategic areas:

- Governance and Planning
- Financial Sustainability
- Volunteer Recruitment and Management
- Partnering & Vendors
- Outreach to Non-R1s and DEIA
- Group Structure and Policy

Day 3 concluded the retreat with a joint session with CASC with presentations on:

- CaRCC and CASC workforce development efforts
- The CaRCC Capabilities Model
- Potential for shared position papers
- Opportunities for increased collaboration between the two organizations

Current areas of strength

The retreat highlighted several areas where CaRCC continues to demonstrate strong performance:

1. Community Growth and Engagement

- Increased engagement beyond R1 institutions
- Strong participation in People Network tracks
- Effective emergence of new working groups from community needs
- Growth of inclusive, actively engaged RCD community

2. Professional Development

- Successful CaRCC Monthly Welcome sessions for new members
- Strong track record of effective group leadership
- Valuable professional development opportunities for RCD staff
- Effective chairs meetings and inter-organizational communication

3. Organizational Infrastructure

- Implementation of Wild Apricot membership management system
- Strong communication and coordination across groups
- Effective governance structure for working groups
- Successful production of papers and community resources

Opportunities for growth and improvement

Several key areas for growth and improvement were identified during the retreat:

1. Membership and Engagement

- Need for clearer membership definitions and structure
- Enhanced strategies for engaging non-R1 and underserved institutions
- Improved recruitment of early-career professionals
- Clear policies for vendor employee engagement
- Better clarification of roles across different group types (People Network, Interest Groups, Working Groups)
- Development of clearer value propositions for different institutional contexts

2. Organizational Structure

- Need for visualization and documentation of CaRCC's organizational model
- Clarification of terminology and operational definitions
- Enhanced project management support
- Clear processes for group evolution (e.g., Interest Groups transitioning to tracks)

3. Volunteer Management

- Creation of comprehensive volunteer handbook
- Development of templates and best practices for group facilitation
- Development of clear role descriptions and time commitments
- Implementation of succession planning processes
- Improved support structures for volunteers

- Recognition systems for volunteer contributions

4. Partnerships and External Relations

- Development of formal partnership frameworks
- Strategic collaboration with RRCOP and other communities
- Structured approach to industry relationships

Funding and sustainability

The retreat made significant progress on CaRCC's future organizational structure and sustainability, with detailed discussions of both immediate needs and long-term funding strategies:

1. Organizational Structure Decision

- Resolved to contract with an existing 501(c)(3) as short-term fiscal sponsor with a goal to become independent 501(c)(3) organization
- Timeline established for updated governance structure with elected Board by June 30, 2025

2. Budget Development Framework

- Identified need for two-tiered budget approach:
 - Bare-minimum/sustaining set of costs for current operations
 - Expanded budget including "nice-to-have" additions and currently in-kind resources
- Key cost categories identified:
 - Non-human operating infrastructure
 - Human effort for operations
 - Legal and accounting resources
 - Insurance and Code of Conduct enforcement
 - Infrastructure scaling costs

3. Potential Revenue Streams

- Individual Memberships:
 - CaRCC is committed to maintaining a free individual membership tier
 - Recommended donation model for non-vendor employees
 - Tiered structure with merchandise incentives
 - No paywalls for essential resources
 - Possible restricted access for certain member content
- Institutional Support:
 - Focus on sponsorship rather than organizational membership
 - Recommended donations based on Carnegie classification
 - Employer-paid individual memberships

- Industry Engagement:
 - General organizational sponsorship
 - Event-specific sponsorship (retreats, Nexus Day)
 - Need to communicate clear value proposition for industry partners

- Professional Services:
 - Training and classes
 - Consulting services
 - Capabilities Model assessments
 - HR Job Family frameworks
 - Department reviews
 - Skills matching program and professional registry

- Grants and Agency Funding:
 - NSF grants for specific projects and workshops
 - Focus on new research and development

4. Implementation Considerations for Obtaining 501(c)(3) Status:

- Need for early legal counsel
- Balance between revenue generation and community access
- Careful consideration of industry partner roles
- Development of professional reports and assessments as member benefits

Priorities and action items

The retreat established specific priorities with assigned ownership:

1. Organizational Structure and Governance

- Establish new governance structure with Board by June 30, 2025 (Owner: Financial Models Group)
- Create visualization of CaRCC organizational model (Owner: Logistics)
- Develop model for group governance and coordination (Owner: Chairs Leadership)
- Clarify membership definitions and structures (Owner: Logistics)

2. Outreach and Inclusion (Owners: Engagement Group, Emerging Centers)

- Develop comprehensive plan for non-R1 institution engagement
- Create strategy for supporting RCSI ongoing engagement
- Establish partnerships with regional and specialized organizations
- Focus on targeted outreach to underserved institutions
- Design approach for regional events and presentations

3. Volunteer Management (Owner: Engagement Group)

- Create recruitment templates and value propositions
- Develop comprehensive volunteer handbook

- Establish clear processes for group management
- Design professional development pathways

4. Partnership Development (Owners: Logistics Group and designated leads)

- Create formal partnership framework
- Establish RRCoP partnership model
- Develop vendor engagement policies
- Define sponsorship guidelines

Next steps

Implementation will begin immediately with several key actions:

1. Financial and Governance

- Financial Models Group to present charter and timelines by December 2024
- Development of initial budget and funding streams
- Begin process of fiscal sponsor selection

2. Community Engagement

- Town Hall scheduled for January 2025
- Developing survey of CaRCC community needs and priorities

3. Documentation and Structure

- Creation of organizational visualization
- Development of volunteer handbook
- Consolidation of group management processes

4. Regular Assessment

- Quarterly review of priority implementation
- Regular updates to co-Chairs and co-Coordiators
- Ongoing evaluation of progress toward 501(c)(3) status

Appendix A

2024 CaRCC Annual Retreat List of Attendees

Adams, Eric – Senior Manager, Purdue University Rosen Center for Advanced Computing
Amritkar, Amit – Technical Director, Penn State
Andino, Gladys – Strategic Services and Education Manager, University of Virginia
Anne, Kirk – Independent Consultant
Booth, Justin M – Senior Manager, Research Cyberinfrastructure MSU IT
Brunson, Dana – Executive Director for Research Engagement, Internet2
Cheatham, Thomas – Professor / Director, University of Utah
Clemins, Patrick – Director, Research Computing and Data, Large Research Initiatives, University of Vermont (Remote)
Combs, Jane – Director, Advanced Research Computing Center, University of Cincinnati
Ellis, Carolyn – Director Research Cybersecurity and Compliance, Arizona State University
Freeman, Bob – Director, Research Technology Operations, Harvard Business School
Gaylord, Clark – Director Research Technology Services, George Washington University
Ghahramani, Forough – Vice President for Research & Innovation, NJ Edge
Grasch, Kimberly – Associate Director-Administration & Faculty Programs, University of Chicago
Haymore, Brian – Sr IT Architect - HPC, University of Utah
Hicks, John – Research Support Engineer, Internet2
Hillery, Betsy – Director of Data Initiatives, Purdue University
Ivey, Susan – [Title not provided], [Institution not provided]
Knepper, Rich – Director, Center for Advanced Computing, Cornell University
Ma, Julie – Program Director, MGHPC
McCaffrey, Deb – Research Facilitator, Arizona State University
McCanse, Daphne – Communications and Outreach Lead, CaRCC/Internet2
Mehring, Susan – Associate Director, Consulting, Cornell Center for Advanced Computing
Michael, Lauren – CI Facilitation Consultant, LMichael Consulting, LLC; Internet2 (contract)
Middelkoop, Timothy – Senior Research Engagement Engineer, Internet2
Milhans, Jackie – Director, Research Computing and Data, Northwestern University
Neeser, Amy – Consulting + Outreach Lead, University of California, Berkeley (Remote)
Porter, Sam – Associate Director, University of Maryland
Reidy, Chris – Facilitation Manager, University of Arizona
Renfro, Mike – HPC Systems Administrator, TN Tech University
Schmitz, Patrick – Principal Consultant, Semper Cogito Consulting
Simms, Jason – Research Computing Manager, Swarthmore College
Smith, Matthew – Manager, Research Systems, University of British Columbia
Stauffer, Ashley – Project Manager, Penn State University
Towns, John – Deputy Director, NCSA/University of Illinois
Weiner, Michael – Research Scientist, Georgia Institute of Technology
Yockel, Scott – University Research Computing Officer, Harvard University